

“Ottoman Map of 1875 and Rendering the Greek Frontier Visible: Constructions of Border Stations and the Beginning of ‘a New Era’”

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Abstract

This article examines an Ottoman map dated 1875 depicting the frontier between the Yanya province and Greece. Preserved in few copies in the Ottoman archives, the map is significant not only as one of the earliest Ottoman-language cartographic representations of the post-1832 border, but also as a layered document of military geography, border infrastructure, and historical imagination. The article argues that the map should be read not simply as a technical rendering of a political boundary, but as a composite frontier document that combines a numbered chain of border towers and forts, and a historical-topographical narrative attached to selected sites. By comparing the map with the earlier boundary commissioners’ map of 1834 and by using GIS-based reconstruction, the study shows that the 1875 Ottoman version presents a more topographically coherent and strategically legible frontier in several disputed sectors. It also demonstrates how the map visualized the border as a materially organized landscape structured by posts, surveillance points, and defensive logic. At the same time, the historical notes on the map reveal an Ottoman narrative of conquest and rule inscribed onto Greek space. The map thus illuminates the late Ottoman transformation of the frontier into a cartographic, military, and ideological object.

Keywords: Ottoman-Greek borders; Greek frontier; border stations, historical cartography, Thessaly, nineteenth century

Introduction

The first Ottoman-Greek border took material form after the work of the boundary commissions and the map they produced in 1834 (signed in 1835). Although both the frontier zone and the map itself were regarded by Ottoman officials as problematic and imperfect, the settlement nonetheless marked an important stage in the effort to stabilize diplomatic relations and contain what was increasingly understood as the “Greek question.”¹ The map was distributed to both sides, signed by the boundary commissioners, and accepted as the basis of the new territorial arrangement. Although the exact drawing of the line, as well as Ottoman objections to parts of it, remained matters of contention for some time, little practical revision followed, and at least at the diplomatic level the issue entered a relatively dormant phase.

On the ground, however, the frontier remained far from stable. The pyramids and other markers reportedly placed by the delimitation commission at ninety-five points along the boundary gradually shifted, disappeared, or were altered according to local needs and pressures. Some were likely moved by villagers dissatisfied with the line; others may simply have decayed or lost their function in a difficult and often weakly supervised terrain.² In this respect, the Ottoman-Greek border does not appear exceptional. Many of the phenomena described by historians of nineteenth-century frontiers, the instability of boundary markers, local interference, and the disjunction between cartographic precision and lived geography, seem to have characterized this frontier as well.

At the same time, the borderlands were being reshaped by demographic mobility. The reciprocal arrangements that enabled population movement after the late 1830s made it possible for people linked by kinship, property, or local networks to cross and settle on either side of the border. The region thus witnessed not only territorial demarcation but also ongoing realignments of population and settlement. Yet these social and demographic processes are not

1. The Ottoman-Greek boundary was examined and politically determined in 1832, while the surveys and the map prepared by the boundary commission were only completed by the spring of 1835. Lieutenant-Colonel George Baker, writing from the perspective of the commission itself, described both the practical difficulties of the demarcation process and the fieldwork undertaken together with the other commissioners, including the Ottoman and Greek representatives. As Baker makes clear, the commission had to rely on Pierre Lapie’s 1826 map, yet he judged it “very defective on all the most important points of the line” and stated that, for the sector between the Gulf of Arta and the Spercheios valley, it bore “not the least resemblance to the real configuration of the ground.” Among the most serious problems, he identified the misplacement of Veluchi and the fictive or displaced Graditza/Granitzas, reproduced in Lapie’s map from earlier travel literature. George Baker, “Memoir on the Northern Frontier of Greece,” *Journal of the Royal Geographical Society of London* 7 (1837): 81–111. George Toliás has more recently situated these defects within the wider making of philhellenic military cartography, showing both the epistemic power and the practical limits of Lapie’s synthesis, especially where conjectural geographical associations had to be translated into an operative cartographic framework. George Toliás, “Military Mapping, Philhellenic Geography, and the Making of Greece, 1811–1827,” *The Historical Review/La Revue Historique* 19, no. 1 (2022 [published 2023]): 117–140.

2. “These landmarks in the inhabited districts at the two extremities were mostly destroyed by the Turks in the winter of 1832; they were restored again in the ensuing summer, and the Greek commissioner attached to the commission being personally acquainted with the sites of each of them, their more solid and permanent restoration was confided to the care of his government.” Baker, p.83.

the subject of this article and deserve separate treatment. The focus here is instead on the visualization of the border and on the parallel process through which the frontier acquired an increasingly militarized and material form, both on paper and on the ground.

Border Materiality - Construction of Border Stations (*Kule in Ott.*)

From its earliest years, the Ottoman-Greek border corresponded to a geography marked by persistent violence. The mountainous zones of northern Greece had already been shaped during the revolutionary period by the activity of irregular armed groups, fluid loyalties, and competing local power structures. Some of these men found positions within the military sphere of the Greek state, while others sought employment under Ottoman authorities responsible for guarding the frontier. Yet this arrangement proved unstable. In the border districts, especially where Albanian-dominated local power networks overlapped with older practices of frontier security, local actors were able for a time to exploit the vacuum produced by imperial transition and military reform. Drawing on their familiarity with the geography, local custom, and armed practice of the region, they imposed a violent and highly flexible border regime, at times confronting brigands, at times collaborating with them, and at times becoming indistinguishable from them.³

By the late 1840s, this condition had become one of the principal issues in Ottoman-Greek diplomatic relations. The Greek frontier increasingly occupied the Ottoman political agenda, not in isolation, but as part of a wider imperial concern with the security and governability of border zones. Comparable anxieties could be observed on other Ottoman frontiers as well, especially those facing Russia and Iran, where questions of surveillance, policing, and strategic preparedness became more pressing in periods of crisis or impending war. The Ottoman-Greek boundary should therefore be understood as part of an empire-wide rethinking of frontier governance under the pressures of modernization, diplomacy, and European intervention. In practice, however, it was the intensification of brigandage in the borderlands that drew the most immediate attention from Ottoman authorities and prompted efforts to strengthen military presence along the frontier, particularly in the western sector, where the mountainous terrain made control more difficult and the problem more acute.

3. For the violence, fluid loyalties, and unstable security arrangements that characterized the early Ottoman-Greek borderlands, see especially Vasilis Gounaris, who emphasizes the persistence of armed local networks and the frontier's entanglement with wider regional power struggles; John Koliopoulos, whose work remains fundamental for understanding the relationship between brigandage, irregular military structures, and Greek irredentism; and George Gavrilis, who situates the Ottoman-Greek boundary within a broader comparative framework of nineteenth-century interstate border-making and shows how such frontiers were transformed into militarized institutions. On the Ottoman side, and particularly on the role of local irregular forces, *derbendat* structures, and the gradual transformation of the frontier into a more centralized and materially organized security regime, see also Dilek Özkan, *Ottoman Perceptions and Considerations on the First Ottoman-Greek Borders in Thessaly, 1832–1865* (PhD diss., University of Athens, Department of History and Archaeology, 2016).

Figure 1. BOA, HRT.h. 216, Ottoman-Greek Boundary Map, prepared by the boundary commission at Argos in 1834, signed in 1835. Scale: 1/150,000. Courtesy of the Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye, State Archives.

It was in this context that the construction of new towers, forts, and guard posts along the border emerged as both a practical and symbolic response. These structures were intended to strengthen the line militarily, discipline movement across it, and impose a more regularized regime of surveillance and control as a measure to the brigandage. Their construction signals an important transformation: the Ottoman-Greek border was no longer conceived only as a line agreed upon through diplomacy, but increasingly as a militarized border regime that had to be materialized, defended, and made visible in space. The map examined in this article belongs precisely to this moment. It offers not simply a representation of the border, but a cartographic rendering of its militarization and of the Ottoman state's effort to convert a contested and unstable borderland into a legible security landscape.⁴

Although the militarization of the Ottoman-Greek frontier, and the process by which the border acquired material visibility through towers, guard posts, and related structures, deserves fuller treatment, this article does not reconstruct that history in its entirety. Instead, it offers a brief summary in order to clarify the context and significance of the map examined here. Ottoman archival documents suggest that the first phase of this process was already underway by the late 1830s, shortly after the completion of the first map of the border region. In a document dated 1838, the governor of the region, Mehmed Emin Paşa (Kıbrıslı), responded to the complaints of the Greek consul, who alleged that the Ottomans had violated Greek

4. The maps discussed here are preserved in the Ottoman State Archives (BOA). In addition to the original boundary commissioners' map, drawn at Argos in 1834 and signed in 1835, the archives also contain an Ottoman Turkish version of Lapie's map (HRT 55), although this appears to be a rather poor copy. On that map, too, the frontier is represented as a drawn line. It should also be noted that the commissioners' original map survives in the same archive under the code HRT 216, with Ottoman Turkish place names written alongside the original toponyms, while HRT 217, dated 1267 (1851), is an Ottoman copy of that same map. Unlike the reduced version more commonly known through Baker's published memoir, the original map preserved in BOA is both much larger and considerably more detailed, and has rarely been referred to as such in the scholarship. After these comes the Ottoman map dated 1291 (1875), whose close resemblance to Kiepert's 1871 map gives the strong impression that it was derived, directly or indirectly, from Kiepert's cartographic model.

territory while constructing a tower at a place called Chelona. Rejecting the accusation, Mehmed Emin Paşa stated that when construction had begun two years earlier, the Ottoman authorities had consulted the Greek border officials, examined the relevant border maps, and proceeded accordingly.⁵ In another document, dated 1843 and relating to the repair of the fortresses of Arta, Preveza, and Parga, some towers located on the western sector of the Greek frontier also appear in the repair calculations and plans.⁶ A further document from 1849, again concerning repairs to fortresses near the Greek border, including those of Arta and Preveza, suggests not only the continuing importance of the older fortifications in the region but also the likely existence of frontier towers established during the border's early years.⁷ After the uprising of 1848, moreover, the reverberations of unrest can once again be traced across the frontier zone. Documents from this period reveal renewed concern with the protection and repair of existing structures, this time particularly in the eastern sector around Lamia, where such installations were at times referred to as *kazarma*.⁸

Another group of documents brings us to the eve of the Crimean War (1853–1856) and to the uprisings of 1854 in Epirus and Thessaly. By the early 1850s, a prolonged dispute had emerged between Ottoman and Greek local authorities over the course of the Surpi river in the frontier zone. The governor of the Greek district of Phthiotis and the Ottoman governor of Trikala both became involved in the matter. According to the Ottoman documentation, a certain Grizanos from the border village of Mitzela altered the riverbed by digging a ditch.⁹ Upon learning of this intervention, Ottoman notables and local officials from Almyros went to the site, examined the area, and restored the river to its previous course by destroying the works

5. BOA, HAT 1221/47759, 29-12-1253 (1838). The document records Mehmed Emin Paşa's response to the Greek consul's allegation that the Ottomans had violated Greek territory while constructing a tower at Chelona. Emin Paşa rejected the claim, arguing that construction had begun two years earlier only after consultation with the Greek border authorities and examination of the border maps.

6. BOA, C.AS 528/22052, 11-02-1259 (1843).

7. BOA, A.}MKT.MVL. 13-54, 11-04-1265 (1849)

8. BOA, HR.MKT. 20-46 07-06-1264 (1848). In Ottoman usage, *kazarma* appears to have remained a marginal and somewhat foreign term rather than a fully assimilated element of the standard bureaucratic or military lexicon. Ottoman documents generally preferred more familiar Turkish designations such as *kule* (tower), *kale* (fortress), or *kışla* (barracks). When *kazarma* does occur, it tends to appear in localized expressions, for example in formulations referring to a place "called *kazarma*" or to towers known by that name, which suggests a vernacular or regional usage rather than one consistently adopted by central Ottoman administrative and military circles. This pattern indicates that local populations used *kazarma* for certain towers or fortifications in their own environment, while the more centralized Ottoman register avoided it. The term nonetheless survived in local memory and remains in use in some regions today, including in place names and even modern hotel or accommodation names. Significantly, *kazarma* is absent from the standard Ottoman dictionaries most commonly consulted, whereas Andreas Tietze's etymological dictionary points to its Italian origin, connecting it to *caserma* and ultimately *casa di arma*, in the sense of a military shelter or barracks. The Greek form *καζάρμα* seems to belong to the same linguistic trajectory. Even so, it should be stressed that the word never became part of widespread or standard Ottoman usage. <https://el.wiktionary.org/wiki/καζάρμα> and also Tietze, Andreas. *Tarihî ve Etimolojik Türkiye Türkçesi Lugatı*. Istanbul: Türkiye Bilimler Akademisi, 2002, vol.2.

9. BOA, A.} DVN.NMH 6-21 29-08-1269. Grizanos should be Giorgos Grizanos, one of the Greek *oplarchigos* connected to the foundation of Amaliapoli. The settlement, named after Queen Amalia, was established by inhabitants originally from Mitzela who moved to the Greek side after the delimitation of the frontier.

attributed to Grizanos.¹⁰ The dispute continued in subsequent years, as the central authorities ordered that the true course of the river be determined in accordance with the maps and the treaty line, and requested that a competent engineer be sent to the region to inspect the site and compare the terrain with the cartographic record. It was in this context that Tevfik Paşa appeared for the first time as an Ottoman official appointed by the center to intervene in the frontier zone. He would later play a more prominent role in the serious efforts to construct new towers and border stations initiated by the Porte in the following years.¹¹

A more intensive phase began in 1853, which coincided with or initiated a broader moment when border security was being reconsidered, the border itself was re-examined, and diplomatic disputes arose over whether the line had been violated. Although the 1854 unrest cannot be reduced simply to a border question, it likely generated new tensions in the border zone.¹² From 1853 onward, however, one can clearly trace an intensified Ottoman effort to re-evaluate, survey, and remap the frontier, and to plan the construction of new towers, forts, quarantine stations, customs buildings, and barracks. In this document, the governor of Trikala, Vasıf Paşa, sets out the details of the proposed construction programme and explains the reasoning behind it on the basis of the survey and calculations carried out by Tevfik Bey two years earlier, in 1851.¹³ According to the plan, the construction of 35 new towers, each intended to accommodate 10 to 17 soldiers, was estimated at 350,000 kuruş. In addition, one barracks at Domokos for the accommodation of 150 soldiers was projected to cost 50,000 kuruş, while three border stations in the Agrafa region, designed to house 120 soldiers, were estimated at 90,000 kuruş. The plan also included 35 smaller signal towers (işarethane), to be placed between the larger stations, at a cost of 3,000 kuruş each, or 105,000 kuruş in total. Altogether, the projected cost of construction amounted to 595,000 kuruş.¹⁴ The document further notes

10. In a personal letter dated 1851, apparently addressed to the local governor of Almyros, probably Hüseyin Ağa, Grizanos complained about Ali Çuka, the *derbendat* officer who had overseen the destruction of the river works. He defended his own actions as a necessary clearing of the riverbed to prevent damage on either side, insisted that both parties knew the true course of the boundary, and condemned Ali Çuka's renewed interference as "childish acts" that produced only "confusion and disturbance." Here an excerpt from his letter with its translation: "Ερωτώ, Χουσειν αγά, αν πάλιν και δευτέραν φοράν έλθη ο Τσουκάς να θέλη να κάμη δέσιν εις το ρεύμα, και ευρεθώμεν και ημείς εκεί, πώς νομίζει ο Αλι Τσουκάς ότι θα πέσωμεν ανασκελά, να τον αφήσωμεν να κάμη ό,τι θέλει; Νομίζω όχι. Χουσειν αγά, την διεύθυνσιν του ρεύματος την ξεύρετε και την ξεύρομεν ποία είναι, και εκεινο το μέρος πρέπει να καθαρισθή, διά να τρέχη το νερό και να μην προξενή βλάβην ούτε εις το εν ούτε εις το άλλο μέρος. Και όχι να καταφεύγετε εις παιδαριώδη κινήματα, τα οποία κανέν άλλο αποτέλεσμα δεν φέρνουν, ειμή συγχύσεις και ταραχές." [I ask, Hüseyin Ağa, if Çuka comes again a second time wishing to make an embankment in the stream, and if we too are there, does Ali Çuka think that we shall simply fall back and allow him to do whatever he wants? I do not think so. Hüseyin Ağa, you know and we know the direction of the stream, and that place must be cleaned so that the water may run and cause damage neither to one side nor the other. Do not resort to childish acts, which produce no other result than confusion and disturbance.] BOA. A.}DVN.NMH 6-21 29-08-1269 (1853), here page 8, 1851.

11. BOA. HR. MKT. 55-62, 14-04-1269 (1853).

12. This remains a subject that requires further investigation, especially through Greek sources, which have tended to focus more heavily on the uprising itself and on its nationalist or irredentist dimensions, while leaving its social, economic, and diplomatic aspects less fully explored.

13. BOA. MVL. 267-60, 25-07-1269 (1853).

14. BOA. MVL. 267-60, 25-07-1269 (1853), page 2.

that the earlier decision to build quarantine stations at Surpi, Derbend-i Furka, and Kara Manoli remained in force. In addition, several border stations are mentioned separately for the Ioannina region. These structures were to be built in a solid manner, with arched vaulting and roofing.¹⁵ However, a later document dated 1857 shows that the plans had been revised considerably. By that point, Mirliva Tevfik Paşa, together with nine senior engineers from Istanbul, had been sent to the frontier to begin construction. In this new version of the programme, the projected works included 58 border stations (*karakol*), 6 barracks, and 45 smaller border posts or signal towers (*işaret kuleleri*)¹⁶, yielding a total of 109 structures.¹⁷

This first phase did not proceed smoothly.¹⁸ The earliest engineers and military personnel sent to the region fell ill during a cholera outbreak and had to withdraw.¹⁹ Subsequent documents record a prolonged administrative and diplomatic process involving newly appointed engineers, the recovery or consultation of earlier maps, joint inspection of the boundary by both sides, and negotiations over earlier border violations that Ottoman officials presented as having been resolved in their favour.²⁰ Yet the archival traffic itself should not obscure the slower pace of implementation on the ground. Only after repeated changes in personnel, the circulation of revised plans and projects, and years of administrative delay do we learn, by 1869, that the new towers and barracks along the frontier had finally been completed.²¹ This was also the moment at which the Ottoman state began stationing regular

15. BOA. A. }MKT. NZD. 85-28, 01-11-1269 (1853).

16. Considering that the first telegraph lines in the Ottoman Empire took place during the Crimean War, in 1855, these signal towers should be considered part of plans to connect the region with the telegraph lines, see: Ayşegül Okan, "The Ottoman Postal and Telegraphic Services in the Last Quarter of the Nineteenth Century", Master Thesis, Boğaziçi University, 2003, p.33.

17. BOA. A. }MKT. MHM. 119-26, 06-03-1274 (1857).

18. Probably by the unrest of 1854 in the region and during the skirmishes between Ottoman soldiers and the Greek irregular forces, some of the already existing and some of during the construction phase were burnt and collapsed. See for instance document BOA. A. }MKT. NZD. 136-60, 14-06-1271 (1855) mentioned that one border tower in Surbi passage and another one in Velestin were burnt, and the barracks in Domoko were repaired. Another document mentions that 60 villages were damaged as a result of unrest of 1854, and from Engineers Education (Hendeshane) Major (binbaşı) İzzet Efendi was appointed to undertake a survey on the damage both on the villages and on the border stations, along the frontier. BOA. A. }MKT. UM. 173-3, 29-02-1271 (1855)

19. Mirliva Tevfik Paşa, together with three major senior engineers and two other engineers from the Ottoman Military Engineering School died following their arrival in the frontier region in the summer of 1857. See: BOA. A. }MKT. UM. 295-50, 04-03-1274 (1857) BOA. A. }MKT. NZD. 284-23, 21-11-1275 (1859).

20. BOA. HR. SYS. 1680-13, 09-04-1853. Although the file of these document series are dated 1853, they are collection of document related to the earlier correspondence regarding the survey of Tevfik Paşa, and discussions about the numbers and types of the buildings that were offered to be built, all delivered to Hurşid Efendi, to would meet with the Greek engineers to re-examine the violations that the Paşa had determined.

21. One of the main reasons for the delay in the post-Crimean War construction programme was the renewed dispute over the status of these two villages, namely whether they should remain on the Ottoman side, as the Ottoman authorities maintained, or fall within Greek territory. During this period, Ottoman representatives were compelled to revisit the earlier discussions concerning these alleged violations of the boundary, and after the death of Tevfik Paşa, Hurşid Bey assumed a central role in the matter. In the second phase of construction, beginning in 1857, when some of the border stations had already been completed and others were under construction, Greek local authorities raised formal objections, at times claiming that certain posts had been placed too close to their territory. In the same context, the Greek consul in Istanbul visited the *Erkân-ı Harbiye* to meet with the Ottoman pasha and discuss the placement of the frontier posts, arguing that the Ottoman installations were too numerous

troops in these structures and, by transforming and effectively dissolving the older *derbendat* system, moved the region toward a more centralized and recognizably modern border regime.

By 1870, the archival record includes letters of appreciation from the assemblies of the Ottoman districts adjacent to the frontier, as well as a letter from the governor of the sancak of Trikala, Halil Rıfat Paşa, stating clearly that, after almost twenty years of planning and repeated attempts, the border stations had finally been completed. In his view, this development would remove one of the most serious obstacles to the security of the province, namely brigandage, together with the parallel and equally exhausting problem of the *başbozuk* troops, that is, irregular forces, with which the province had struggled for some forty years. Halil Paşa described this moment as “*bir tarih-i cedid-i asayiş*,” adding that these works should be counted among the achievements of the imperial government. His phrasing suggests the opening of a new era of order and security, and, more broadly, a new phase in the history of Thessaly.²²

For the Ottoman government, the larger aim was clear: to render the Greek frontier secure, legible, and, if possible, definitive. It was in this context that the map studied in this article was likely produced. Bearing the signature of the *Erkân-ı Harbiye* and dated 1291 Rumi (1875), this map of the Yanya vilayet and its border with Greece appears to be one of the earliest and rare Ottoman-language cartographic renderings of the post-1835 Ottoman-Greek frontier.²³ Its significance lies not merely in its rarity, but in the way it visualizes a frontier that had, by this stage, become increasingly surveyed, fortified, and politically charged. The following sections therefore turn from the construction history itself to the map’s contents and to the distinct forms of frontier knowledge it sought to assemble on a single surface. The emergence of modern cartography and the Ottoman Empire’s growing engagement with it is

and too solidly built, especially in comparison with the Greek side, where the existing structures were said to consist merely of small huts rather than proper border stations. BOA. HR. SYS. 1680-13, 1857, p. 31. In the following years, the Greek authorities appear to have intensified their pressure on the Ottoman government in an effort to hinder or limit this programme of construction, invoking the need to preserve a balance of power in the border region. See: BOA. MVL. 957-9, 16-05-1279 (1862) This reaction may suggest that the Greek side felt increasingly insecure in the face of Ottoman preparations, or at least regarded such a more heavily militarized frontier as incompatible with its own long-term aspirations to push the border northward and incorporate regions such as Thessaly, where populations identified as their ethnic kin still lived under Ottoman rule.

22. BOA. İ.MTZ.(01) 16-493, Rumi: 16-10-1287 (1870) Although Halil Rıfat Paşa’s letter also refers to a list identifying the locations of the newly constructed border stations together with the names assigned to them, the archival dossier containing these documents does not include that list. Nor does it preserve the images and maps reportedly prepared by an officer and collected by the chief of staff of the Imperial Third Army at Monastir (Bitola), Mirliva Rıfat Paşa, head of the *Erkân-ı Harbiye* of the *Ordu-yı Hümâyün*.

23. Two separate copies of this map survive in the Ottoman Archives under different catalogue codes. The first is preserved as BOA. Y.PRK.M 1/80 (1297). Although the map itself still bears the original date of 1291, the annotations added within the frame show that a new boundary line was later drawn by hand in order to indicate the territory ceded to Greece following the Berlin settlement. The stamp and accompanying notes are dated 1297, making clear that this copy was reused during the border revision process. The second copy is preserved as BOA, Y.PRK.M 4/97. Although it also carries the later date 1321 L. 24 (19 January 1904), the stamp and the dates written next to the annotations clearly indicate Şevval 1297 in the Hijri calendar and Eylül 1296 in the Rumi calendar, that is, September 1880. The accompanying description likewise suggests that this copy, too, was in use during the discussions surrounding the Berlin settlement. These annotations will be examined in greater detail in later sections of this article.

now much better understood thanks to recent scholarship.²⁴ It is increasingly clear that from the late eighteenth century onward Ottoman officials were not only aware of developments in European cartographic and engineering sciences, but also conscious of the empire's relative shortcomings in these fields and eager to address them. The establishment first of the *Hendesehane* and later of the *Mühendishane-i Berrî-i Hümâyün*, together with the arrival of engineers and instructors from France, created the institutional framework within which Ottoman students received training in cartography, topography, and modern engineering.²⁵ Some of the earliest products of this educational transformation, maps likely prepared by Ottoman engineering students, still survive today in the Ottoman archives. By the mid-nineteenth century, this earlier phase had given way to a more mature structure, in which mapmaking assumed a more specialized place within the *Erkân-ı Harbiye*, and Ottoman engineers took a more active role in military cartography and in boundary commissions.²⁶ As a result, the archives preserve an increasingly rich corpus of Ottoman maps, especially from the second half of the nineteenth century, when war, treaty-making, and the growing political centrality of frontier management generated an ever greater demand for cartographic production.

24. Mirela Altić, “Nineteenth-Century Ottoman Topographic Mapping of the Balkans.” *The Cartographic Journal* 55, 2018.(4): 326–40. doi:10.1080/00087041.2018.1548189, Pınar Emiralioğlu, *Geographical Knowledge and Imperial Culture in the Early Modern Ottoman Empire*. Farnham, UK: Ashgate, 2014, Ahmet T. Karamustafa, “Military, Administrative, and Scholarly Maps and Plans”, in *the History of Cartography*, vol. 2, book 1. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1992.

25. Fikret Sarıcaoğlu, “Administrative Cartography in the Ottoman Empire”, in *the History of Cartography*, Volume 4, 64-69. Illinois: University of Chicago Press, Chicago (IL), USA, 2019.

26. Fikret Sarıcaoğlu, "Boundary Surveying in the Ottoman Empire", in *the History of Cartography*, Volume 4, Illinois: University of Chicago Press, Chicago (IL), USA, 2019, pp.199-203.

Figure 2. Ottoman map of 1875 showing the first Ottoman-Greek border of 1832. This copy, preserved without later annotations, is held in the Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye State Archives, National Security Archive, 110-9-1-2 (1875). Scale: 1/500,000. Courtesy of the Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye, State Archives.

An Ottoman Map of Greek Frontier (1875)

The 1875 Ottoman map of the Greek frontier should be situated within this broader context. Its significance, however, lies not only in its place within the history of Ottoman cartographic development, but also in what it reveals about the relationship between visual representation and geopolitics. Even before turning to its details, it is important to note that this map was more than a technical product. Like other Ottoman maps from earlier periods, it seems to have functioned as an instrument serving additional purposes, among them the communication of political and strategic messages. In technical terms, the map does not necessarily represent a dramatically advanced cartographic achievement by the standards of its time. It would be difficult to argue that it introduced particularly innovative surveying techniques or an unusually sophisticated graphic language. Yet this is not where its importance chiefly lies. Rather, it stands out as one of the earliest Ottoman-language maps to render the post-1835 Ottoman-Greek border through an explicitly Ottoman visual and political lens.

What is striking at first glance is the boldness with which the border is drawn and differentiated. Through its colours and sharply marked dividing line, the map presents the frontier as a highly legible territorial separation. A closer view reveals an additional and even more important feature: along the boundary line itself, one encounters a sequence of numbered points, marked by small boxed or fort-like symbols. These numbered sites, seventy-seven in total, run from east to west.²⁷ The sequence begins on the coast near Almyros, continues through the hills around Sourpi, ascends into the Othrys mountain range, and then follows an inland line stretching toward the area of present-day Lake Plastiras. From there it proceeds toward the Agrafa zone, passing places such as Zaharaki Vrisi and Ithome, and continues onward through the line leading to Plati and Kompoti, before terminating in the direction of Menidi. Even before one considers the separate list of towers and forts included on the right side of the map in a separate box, this numbered chain already suggests that the frontier was

27. The material remains of the Ottoman-Greek frontier and the sustained programme of construction along it remain little known. I have discussed aspects of these frontier towers in (removed for anonymity) and in another article currently under review, although neither study was yet able to take this map into account. More recently, however, the former border has begun to attract renewed local interest. Particularly important in this regard is Stefanos Stamelos's travel-based work (*Apo ton Pagasitiko eos ton Ambrakiko, ena odoiporiko stap rota sinora tis Elladas*, Ekdotikos Oikos S.I. Zacharopoulos, Athens, 2018.) which has helped draw attention to surviving remains along the line, including sites he identifies as former *kazarma*. At the same time, efforts by the Greek Ministry of Culture and researchers such as Georgios Stamopoulos have contributed to the identification, documentation, and official registration of these structures as historical sites. Taken together, these developments suggest that the former Ottoman-Greek frontier is now emerging as a promising field for future research, especially while many of its remains, however fragmentary, are still visible in the landscape.

being rendered not merely as a continuous line, but as a sequence of strategic, observable, and meaningful points distributed across the landscape.

Although the map does not provide a legend and offers no explicit explanation of these symbols, the numbered sites along the frontier most likely refer to Ottoman towers or border stations. Strictly speaking, this cannot be stated with absolute certainty on the basis of the map alone. Yet several features strongly support such an interpretation. Most importantly, these symbols are generally located on the pink to light-red side of the boundary, which marks Ottoman territory, while the Greek side is distinguished in light green. With only a few exceptions, nearly all of them are positioned directly on or immediately adjacent to the thick boundary line itself. Taken together, these visual cues make it highly probable that the numbered points denote Ottoman frontier installations.

At the same time, the total of seventy-seven numbered points does not correspond numerically to the sixty towers and forts listed by name in the boxed register on the right side of the map. The map therefore does not allow us to determine with certainty whether the total number of such structures was sixty, seventy-seven, or some other figure. One possible explanation is that, in addition to the sixty named towers and forts, other types of installations also existed along the frontier, such as customs posts, quarantine stations, barracks, or related structures. Since the map does not clearly distinguish between these categories, however, the exact identity of the remaining seventeen sites cannot yet be established.

Figure 3. Probable Ottoman border stations identified from the 1875 map and projected onto a modern satellite base in Google Earth. The numbered points correspond to the sequence marked on the Ottoman map and provide a preliminary reconstruction of the border stations (*karakols*). While the precise identification of every site requires further field verification, the pattern visible here is already

significant. The stations form an extended and coherent chain along the border zone, concentrating especially at topographically strategic locations such as mountain ridges, passes, valley entrances, and coastal approaches.

Figure 4. Reconstructed border line based on the 1875 Ottoman map, projected onto a modern satellite image. The line follows the route indicated by the Ottoman map and approximates the frontier as it appears to have been understood in practice, especially in sectors where the earlier commissioners' map diverges from the terrain.

Comparison of the frontier lines, reviewing contested locations

A comparison of the two maps, once georeferenced and placed onto Google Earth, makes it possible to locate the marked points on the later Ottoman map, that is, the probable positions of the frontier posts, in relation to the earlier Argos map of 1834.²⁸ The problem lay above all in the disputed twenty-second and twenty-third points of the boundary. During the delimitation process, the Ottoman commissioner, Koniçalı Hüseyin Bey, had objected to the locations assigned by the other commissioners, judged them erroneous, and, after disagreement within

28. The latter, produced by the European boundary commission and signed in 1835, was presumably intended to be delivered to the representatives of both states. Yet its status on the Ottoman side remained ambiguous from the outset. It appears that this original version of the first Ottoman-Greek boundary map, signed by the commissioners, was not available even to Greek historians who have worked on the development of Greek cartography. In most cases, they seem to have relied instead on the smaller printed version published together with Baker's memoir rather than on the larger and more detailed original preserved in the Ottoman archives. For one such example, see Evangelos Liveratos, *Chartografikes Peripeteies tis Elladas, 1821–1919* (Athens: Elliniko Logotechniko kai Istoriko Archeio, 2009), 93.

the commission, left the proceedings and returned to Istanbul to report the matter to the Porte. The work of delimitation continued without him, but the resulting map was not regarded by the Ottoman side as fully acceptable. Reşid Pasha therefore demanded that a new commission be appointed and sent to the field in order to re-examine and remark on the boundary. As far as can be seen, this never happened, despite persistent Ottoman pressure. In practice, the frontier remained in force as it had been fixed, including in the disputed sector extending as far as the point where the Karitsa River, today associated with the Plastiras basin, descended into the plain.

The matter resurfaced in a new form in 1851, when the frontier was once again taken up for review and the construction of new guard posts along the border was decided upon. It was in this context that the earlier Argos map re-entered Ottoman administrative use. An Ottoman-language copy of the 1834 Argos map, now preserved in the Ottoman Archives under HRT 217 and dated 1267/1851, shows that engineers of the *Mühendishane-i Berrî-i Hümayun* were instructed to locate, recover, and reproduce the original commission map. This Ottoman copy is almost exact, which is significant in itself: a map that had once been diplomatically contested nonetheless continued to serve as the technical basis for later Ottoman work on the frontier.

Figure 5. Detail from the 1834 boundary commissioners' map, georeferenced in Google Earth, showing the western sector of the first Ottoman-Greek frontier from Menidi toward the Komboti river and the inland mountain zone. The numbered markers indicate the boundary points placed along this section of the line.

At the same time, comparison between the 1834 Argos map and the 1875 Ottoman military map reveals an important cartographic discrepancy. From approximately the sixteenth point onward, the Argos map appears to misrepresent the course of the frontier in this sector. Whereas the line should have continued farther north, or rather reflected the northern course

by which the frontier was in practice understood and used, it seems instead to deviate too far south in its attempt to reach Mount Boutzikaki, thereby distorting the area up to roughly the twenty-ninth point. This error seems to have been reproduced in many later maps derived from the Argos model. By contrast, the map that appears to correct this zone most successfully is Kiepert's map of 1871, and it is difficult not to suspect that the Ottoman map of 1875 drew, directly or indirectly, on that improved cartographic representation.

Figure 6. Georeferenced reconstruction of the 1834 boundary commissioners' map in Google Earth, showing the full sequence of 95 boundary markers placed along the first Ottoman-Greek frontier from the Gulf of Arta to the Gulf of Volos.

This is precisely where the 1875 Ottoman map becomes especially important. In the disputed sector, it places the line of frontier posts considerably farther north, thereby aligning the border more closely with what appears to have been the actual and practical frontier as it had come to be used on the ground. In this respect, the Ottoman map seems to abandon the erroneous southern displacement inherited from the earlier Argos tradition and instead adopts a more accurate rendering of the contested zone. The point corresponding to no. 16 on the Argos map appears on the Ottoman map as no. 59, and the section that continues from there to approximately no. 43 presents the Ottoman-Greek border in a way that is markedly closer to the frontier's real course. This, in turn, brings into sharper focus the technical limitations of the 1834 Argos map, which now appears to have contained a major shift and distortion in this section.

The implications are considerable. The long-disputed question of Belokomidi and Paliokaritsi, which Ottoman officials had already recognized as problematic in the years immediately preceding the Thessalian unrest of 1853–54, can be better understood in light of this corrected spatial representation. Although these two villages had once figured in Ottoman

arguments as places that ought to have fallen on the Ottoman side, the 1875 map shows clearly that, in practical terms, the frontier posts had by then been drawn up to a line that left both villages on the Greek side. In other words, the Ottoman map appears to have incorporated, and effectively normalized, what had previously been a diplomatically disputed but practically operative frontier. The 1875 rendering thus suggests that the Ottoman state had, by this stage, accepted on the ground a boundary line that had earlier remained controversial in negotiation.

Figure 7. Detail of the 1834 and 1875 border maps in the Karitsa River sector, showing the relationship between the 1834 boundary markers and the probable Ottoman border-station sites indicated on the 1875 map. The figure highlights the cartographic deviation between the two representations in the villages of Belokomidi and Paliokaritsa, a disputed stretch of the frontier that became the subject of Ottoman-Greek controversy in the 1850s.

Seen in this light, the map also speaks directly to the chronology of frontier militarization. The long process of constructing and completing the border posts, a process whose outlines can be followed in the archival record, appears here as materially realized. The map offers visual confirmation that by 1875, after decades of surveying, dispute, redesign, and gradual implementation, the frontier had at last become legible not only as a line debated at the diplomatic table, but as a chain of built installations rendered visible across the landscape. Nearly forty years after the first delimitation, and at a moment when a new revision of the border was already beginning to enter political discussion, the Ottoman-Greek frontier appears on this map as a fully materialized regime of posts, towers, and strategic points. It is precisely this belated visibility, emerging after years of contestation between paper, terrain, and diplomacy, that gives the map its particular historical force.

Table 1 lists the Ottoman names of the frontier posts as recorded on the left-hand side of the map.²⁹ The relationship between these names and nearby settlements or topographical features is generally clear. In most cases, the names appear to have been derived either from adjacent villages and localities or from prominent geographical markers. A large number of them are clearly Ottoman renderings of Greek place names. Establishing their exact equivalents on the modern map, however, will require a separate and more systematic effort. As in many other parts of Greece, place names in this region underwent significant changes over time, making direct identification a complex task.

Table 1. Ottoman names of border stations on the 1874 map

Number	Ottoman script	Modern transliteration
1	چنگل	Çengel
2	کفالوس	Kefalos
3	ارمدریدیا	Armirdya
4	عزیزیه بیوک	Aziziye Büyük
5	استغنو	İstegno
6	غومینو قلہسی	Gümino
7	وریمون	Verimon
8	مغالیرای	Megaliray
9	محمود پاشا	Mahmud Paşa
10	علی پاشا	Ali Paşa
11	لفکر	Lefkar
12	درامالی بیوک	Dramalı Büyük
13	یلدز	Yıldız
14	ماہتاب	Mehtab
15	فضلی	Fazlı
16	چوقہ تپہ	Çuka Tepe
17	دیازمو	Diyazmo
18	حسین عونی پاشا	Hüseyin Avni Paşa
19	تپہ	Tepe
20	سن ایلپا	Sen İliya
21	دریشتیلا	Diriştıla
22	پیشلورہ	Pişilora
23	ادہم پاشا	Edhem Paşa
24	ایلا دیوری	Ayla Divari
25	قاقاون	Kakavun
26	آندہ نیچہ	Andiniça
27	پالامہ	Palama
28	فورقہ دربند	Furka Derbend
29	جامالی	Cemali
30	عمر پاشا	Ömer Paşa
31	استراون	İstravun
32	قروغون	Karagun
33	یورت	Yurt
34	اسعد پاشا	Esad Paşa
35	پالوازوج	Palvazuç

29. I was fortunate to receive invaluable help from Prof. Elias Kolovos in identifying many of these place names. His expertise in deciphering such difficult toponyms is truly remarkable. I am especially grateful to him.

36	عمر پاشا	Ömer Paşa
37	پاپیلا	Papila
38	ایفالا	İfala
39	عزالدین افندی	İzzeddin Efendi
40	تیمبانو	Timbano
41	زهرالی چشمه	Zahara Çeşme
42	ولغارا	Vulgara
43	بالو اپیدیا	Palo Apıdıya
44	مولوچه	Moloha
45	دیپلا	Dipla
46	عبدی پاشا	Abdi Paşa
47	ایتامو	İtamo
48	پاپا دیاری	Papa Diyari
49	کستنیایا	Kastanya
50	پالقور	Palikor
51	میخاری کپیری	Minhari Köprü
52	قره مانولی	Kara Manoli
53	استنفون چشمه	İstingon Çeşme
54	شمونا بوری	Şimona Boru
55	وریمووریشی	Vrimovirişi
56	احورنان	Ahorman
57	اشلیپانه	İşlipane
58	پتریلی	Petrili
59	پلاتانیا	Platanya
60	ویرمونر	Virimoner

At the same time, the nomenclature of the posts also reveals an explicitly Ottoman commemorative layer. Some of the sites bear the names of Ottoman sultans and pashas. The site identified on the map as Aziziye Kalesi, for example, corresponds to the structure built at Surpi, which appears more commonly in the sources as the Armiye (Almyros) Barracks; its name clearly derives from Sultan Abdülaziz. Another post appears to have been named after his son, İzzeddin Efendi. In addition, the names of several Ottoman pashas are also represented, among them Ali Pasha, Ömer Pasha, and Esad Pasha. The naming of these frontier structures therefore reflects not only local geographical reference points, but also a symbolic Ottoman vocabulary of authority and sovereignty.³⁰

A comparable pattern appears in another Ottoman map, more precisely in a hand-drawn sketch of the region between Arta and Preveza. There, the two guard towers previously built along the road from Arta to Salagora are likewise identified as *Mecidiye Kulesi*. This naming convention similarly suggests that they were constructed before 1867. Returning, in light of this earlier sketch, to the discrepancy between the seventy-seven numbered points marked on the 1875 Ottoman map and the sixty towers and forts listed separately in its boxed register, it

30. BOA. I. MTZ. (01). 16-493, 14 Teşrinsani 1286. Trikala governor Halil Rifat, mentions in his letters that they gave proper names according to their locations and they wanted to appreciate also some important personalities, and he clearly states that the most important and the biggest of these buildings was named after Sultan Abdulaziz.

becomes plausible to suggest that at least some of these structures were erected at different moments and belonged to different phases of frontier construction.

As noted earlier in this article, some of these structures had already been built, or had begun to be built, by the late 1830s, especially along the western sector of the frontier, from the Gulf of Arta toward the Agrafa region. Archival documents also indicate the existence of several towers in the eastern sector, particularly around Surpi and Armiye/Almyros, already by 1843, and more clearly still in the correspondence between the governor of Trikala and the Ottoman center between 1851 and 1853. On the basis of these documents, one can calculate the projected construction of 39 border stations (*karakol*) and military barracks, together with 35 smaller border posts (*işarethane*), yielding a total of 74 structures. Later documentation from the 1860s, however, suggests that these numbers changed, especially with regard to the larger border stations. It therefore remains impossible, at present, to establish their full number with certainty. Our archival research has not yet produced evidence sufficient to move substantially beyond this provisional picture. Further materials may emerge in the future, whether through newly accessible archival collections or through work in other archives.

For the time being, and for the period before the frontier revision of 1878, the clearest visual evidence for the existence of these towers prior to the 1875 map remains this sketch of the Gulf of Arta region.³¹ Although the archival catalogue assigns it the date 1341 AH, this appears to be an artificial attribution supplied by archive staff in the absence of an explicit date on the sketch itself. Since the sketch uses the name *Mecidiye Kulesi*, and since it clearly marks the first Ottoman-Greek frontier, I would suggest that it should instead be treated as pre-1878, and quite possibly even pre-1870. The sketch marks a total of seventeen towers, of which seven, clearly identifiable as frontier towers, extend along the Kompoti river line.

31. BOA. HRT-h. 354 1341 (1923).

Figure 8. Detail from the right-hand side of the sketch. On the upper side of the river appears the note: “devlet-i ‘aliyye tarafından müceddeden inşa olunan kuleler” (“towers newly constructed by the Ottoman state”); on the lower side of the river: “işbu nehir Yunan hududunu tasdik eder” (“this river confirms the Greek boundary”). BOA, HRT.h. 354, 1341. Courtesy of the Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye, State Archives.

Figure 9. Sketch of the Gulf of Arta region. Although the archival catalogue dates the document to 1341 AH (1923), this date appears to be an archival attribution and not necessarily the original date of the sketch. BOA, HRT.h. 354. Courtesy of the Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye, State Archives.

Historical Topographies of Greek Antiquity and Ottoman Conquest on the Frontier Map

If the towers and fortified sites along the frontier form one crucial layer of the map, the text placed on the left-hand side of the sheet clearly requires a separate section and a different mode of analysis. Here, one encounters a list of twenty-six place names selected from different parts of the map, each accompanied by a historical note. Taken together, these entries amount to what may be described as a condensed Ottoman narrative of conquest and domination, organized through a historical topography of the Greek lands. Yet this narrative is striking not only because it recalls Ottoman victories. Even where it begins with references to ancient Greek history, with places such as Marathon, Thermopylai, Salamis, and Plataiai, it presents Greek geography less as the triumphant homeland of classical civilization than as a repeatedly

invaded and conquered landscape, successively occupied by Persians, Spartans, Romans, and ancient Macedonians, and repeatedly subjected to the rule of others.³²

This framing becomes even more explicit when the text turns to the Ottoman past. The conquests associated with Mehmed II and Bayezid I are invoked as part of a recognizable Ottoman memory of expansion, while sites such as Yenişehir, Athens, and Eğriboz are recalled through the language of incorporation into Ottoman dominion. In the case of Preveza and the Suli mountains, the narrative shifts to Tepedelenli Ali Pasha, presenting these regions through the suppression of rebels and the restoration of order. The example of Mesolongi in turn recalls the Greek War of Independence, describing how the Greeks who had shut themselves into the fortress were overcome by the assault of Ottoman and Egyptian troops. The list also includes more recent episodes: places such as Domokos, Kalabaka, Fener, and Platanya are linked to the events of 1273 AH (1853–54), when, according to the text, Greek brigands besieged local forts only to be “dispersed” by Ottoman forces. In this way, the section constructs, through twenty-six named locations, a layered historical-topographical narrative that moves from antiquity to the nineteenth century, always from the perspective of the Ottoman state.

What makes this section especially important is the sense that it was doing more than merely providing historical information. In the political atmosphere of the 1870s, such a text seems to have been intended to convey a message. Why should a frontier map include a historical narrative of this kind, one that so insistently revives the memory of Ottoman conquest? At least in part, the answer may lie in the intended audience and in the political work that such memory could perform. The provinces of Epirus and Ottoman Thessaly still contained, relative to other regions, a socially and economically significant Muslim population, one situated in a borderland increasingly shaped by proximity to Europe and to a Europeanizing Greek state. In such a setting, the map may be read as an attempt to reaffirm Muslim-Ottoman attachment to the region by invoking an older imperial past, projecting an image of the Ottoman state as both protector and historical sovereign. At the same time, the text appears to engage, if polemically, with the modern Greek identification with antiquity, a process deeply bound up with the Greek Revolution and with nearly a century of European philhellenism. Reading this in this light, the map seems almost to say: if modern Greeks claim the legacy of ancient Greece, they must also accept the long history of conquest to which that same geography had been subjected.

Perhaps most strikingly, the text also suggests that by the 1870s the Ottoman authors of the map had themselves come to accept, at least in functional terms, the identification of modern Greece with ancient Greece. Despite the two millennia separating the classical world from the contemporary kingdom, the narrative treats the Greeks of the present frontier as

32. The selection of sites such as Marathon, Thermopylai, Salamis, and Plataiai was not without precedent. Such places had already occupied a privileged position in the late eighteenth-century cartographic visualization of Greek space, especially in Barbié du Bocage’s atlas prepared for the *Voyage du jeune Anacharsis* and in Rigas Velestinlis’ Charta, where ancient battlefields and emblematic locations were mobilized as historical-topographic anchors of the Greek past. See: Liveratos, p. 47-52

though they stood in direct continuity with the Greeks of antiquity. In that sense, the map does not merely reject Greek historical claims; it also reveals the extent to which Ottoman political and intellectual discourse had begun to internalize the very historical equation on which modern Greek national identity rested. What emerges, then, is not a simple counter-narrative, but a more complex cartographic text, one that appropriates the temporal depth of Greek antiquity while reinscribing it within an Ottoman story of conquest, subjugation, and imperial legitimacy.

Figure 10. BOA. Y.PRK.M 4-97 1291 (1875). One of the annotated copies of the 1875 Ottoman military map of the Ottoman-Greek frontier, likely reused during the decision-making procedures that led to the boundary revision of 1881, by which the frontier was shifted northward and most of Thessaly was ceded to Greece following the Treaty of Berlin (1878). As indicated in the legend at the bottom of the map, the coloured lines represent successive border proposals and decisions: the solid blue line marks the line stipulated by the Berlin Treaty of 1878; the dark green dashed line indicates the Ottoman government's position of March 1879; the yellow dashed line represents the British proposal; the solid green line shows a further Ottoman proposal advanced in 1879; the red dashed line marks the renewed Greek proposal; the solid black line indicates the French proposal; the solid orange line represents the decision of the Berlin Conference in 1881; the solid yellow line marks a revised Ottoman position of September 1881; and the light grey line indicates a further Ottoman proposal dated October 1881. Courtesy of the Presidency of the Republic of Türkiye, State Archives.

Reusing the Map in an Age of Territorial Loss

This historical narrative becomes even more striking when placed against the political reality in which the map continued to circulate. In practical terms, one may assume that a map printed by the *Erkân-ı Harbiye* press must once have existed in multiple copies, even if only a small number have so far been identified. At present, I have located four copies of the same map, each preserved under a different archival reference. The cleanest copy, apparently unused and preserved as a single sheet, is held in the Ottoman military archive within the catalogue of the 1875 Ottoman-Serbian-Montenegrin War. By contrast, the other copies, now preserved in two separate sheets in the Yıldız collection of the Ottoman Archives, bear annotations, seals, and coloured boundary lines indicating that they were reused during the discussions surrounding the frontier revision of 1881. These later copies make clear that by 1296 AH (1879-1880) the map had become a working instrument for Ottoman commissions and statesmen engaged in evaluating alternative proposals for the new border, decided by the Berlin Treaty of 1878.

This later use creates a striking tension with the historical text discussed above. On the one hand, the left-hand panel revives an Ottoman memory of conquest and presents Greek geography as a landscape repeatedly subdued, occupied, and brought under imperial control. On the other hand, the annotated copies reveal that this same map was being used at a moment when the Ottoman Empire was itself negotiating territorial loss and preparing to relinquish parts of that very geography. In this sense, the map contains a concealed counter-narrative: beneath its language of Ottoman victory lies the political reality of an empire in retreat. The result is a document marked by a profound dissonance between imperial memory and geopolitical decline.

Last but not least, the map reinforces the importance of the Ottoman-Greek border within the military geography of the late Ottoman Empire, where this frontier had come to occupy a distinct place not only in border policy and military planning, but also in the formal curriculum of military education. Ottoman archival documentation confirms this strategic significance. Among the official examination questions prepared for selected students of the Imperial Military Academy, the Naval Academy, the Artillery School, the Imperial Medical School, and the Imperial Preparatory School for the academic year 1286 (1869–70), one question in military geography required candidates to define and describe the imperial boundary with Greece and to identify the points along it that should be held in conditions of attack and defense. The inclusion of such a question in an official examination suggests that, by the late nineteenth century, the Ottoman-Greek frontier had become not merely a line to be guarded, but an object of formal strategic knowledge within the military curriculum.³³

33. “Asâkir-i Berriye Mekteb-i Harbiyesi Şâkirdânına İrâd Olunacak Es’ile Coğrafya-yı askerî: Suâl 4- Memâlik-i şâhânenin Yunanistan ile olan hudûdun ta’rîf ve tavsîfi; ta’arruz ve tedâfîi hâlinde hudûd-ı mezbûre üzerinde tutulması lâzım gelen noktaların beyânı.” BOA. PLK.p, 1072, 22 March 1871.

Conclusions

This article has argued that the Ottoman map of 1291/1874–75 should be read not merely as a technical representation of the Ottoman-Greek frontier, but as a layered document of border knowledge, military organization, and imperial historical imagination. By bringing together a numbered chain of frontier points, a separate register of towers and forts, and a historical-topographical narrative attached to selected sites, the map reveals how the border had come to be conceived as far more than a diplomatic line. It had become a materially organized and strategically legible frontier landscape.

At the same time, the map makes visible the long and uneven process through which the first Ottoman-Greek boundary was transformed after its initial delimitation. GIS comparison with the earlier commissioners' map suggests that the 1874 rendering did not simply reproduce an inherited line, but reflected a more practical and topographically informed understanding of the frontier, especially in sectors that had remained controversial. In this sense, the map captures the border after decades of dispute, revision, construction, and military adaptation to the terrain.

Yet the document also does something more. Through its historical annotations, it reorders Greek space within an Ottoman narrative of conquest, subjugation, and imperial memory. If the earlier philhellenic and Greek cartographic tradition had used historical topography to monumentalize the ancient past, this map appears to answer that same geography from a different political position, reinscribing it within an Ottoman imperial frame. The result is a frontier map that was at once strategic, historical, and ideological.

Finally, the later reuse of some copies during the border revision process of 1880–81 gives the map an additional significance. What had originally functioned as a cartographic expression of Ottoman control over the first frontier was subsequently turned into a working surface for negotiating territorial loss. The map therefore stands at the intersection of two moments: the consolidation of a militarized frontier and the beginning of its revision. Precisely for this reason, it offers an unusually rich insight into the ways the late Ottoman state sought to define, defend, visualize, and ultimately renegotiate one of its most politically charged borders.

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